

Excellent quality open source code can be extremely successful with the proper social code to support it

Open source code and content

By THOMAS HOBERG

Open source has become the dominant form of executed code and content; it is freely shared without costly licences and is available in greater quantity than what is commercially created. Behind both code and content is the fundamental social urge of humanity, to always offer something with minimal prompting. To create the most excellent open source software, it takes sophisticated social code; extremely well curated, wide and deep bodies of knowledge like Wikipedia and the big data economy treasure troves of social media.

As digitalization diffuses the majority of human interaction for the majority of people, the role of the social code around open source becomes much more important and far more political as it applies to, and even steers, more and more of us. This makes it a central topic for social, political and economic sciences as well as computer science.

Key insights

- A million people each contributing just a little created Linux and Wikipedia. Getting a million people to agree on a common cause requires social code few can create.
- Open source has become as diverse as it has become huge and the difference between code and content is disappearing.
- Software giants have turned to eliminating competitors via zero-revenue open source on one hand, while holding customers captive with proprietary vertical code on the other.
- Open source software is resilient even in times of conflict.
- Sharing knowledge, experience and open source with less bias helps to create trust and reduce tension everywhere, even at political level.

Key recommendations

- Europe needs to provide freely the critical open software components that have the extra qualities it wants: privacy compliance, sustainability, support for multiple sovereignties. Compromising on EU values must not be cheaper than using what the EU provides to enable open competition for value created on top of this platform.
- Digital commodities so universally used that they become the public space, need to be transferred to public control and therefore regulated, maintained and taxed if necessary.
- Digital commodities need to be maintained as free open source; components can be given to companies much like public tenders for other infrastructure.
- Europe needs the ability to maintain a fork or EU branch for digital commodities. That takes critical mass and that critical mass needs to be maintained in government, military and education, who must favour those solutions over proprietary ones.
- Evolution of commodities is a strategic asset and needs to play to the ground rules, with diversity being a necessary inclusion.

Open collaboration is human

The overwhelming success of the human species comes from its ability to turn collaboration into an advantage far more important than agility, efficiency of metabolism, keenness of senses, strength, or resilience. The ability to learn, retain and communicate impressions, opinions and knowledge to our kin, more recently across time and around the globe, has allowed us to profit far beyond what any individual could ever learn alone. At its base is an altruistic readiness to share experience with minimal prompting, perhaps an outgrowth of the parental instinct, without which complex organisms could not evolve. As imitation and the following of shared advice turn into success, they transmute from chatter into knowledge that is passed on as tales and gets encoded into legends which form the fabric of societies. Abstraction turns legends into research, which engineers can build into industries, creating entirely new sources of knowledge and bodies of science, a collective genius beyond individual imagination, which is now augmented, accelerated, propagated and harvested by code running on computers.

Greed is just as human as altruism; we're much less likely to gossip about a patch of juicy berries or a hidden cookie jar, when we know we'll be hungry again tomorrow. Withholding knowledge or tradecraft comes naturally, especially when social distance and competition for scarce resources increase. Unilateral knowledge on how to start fire, plant crops and create superior tools, products and weapons decided the fate of our ancestors vs. their opponents, but only until the competition caught up.

As societies evolved and functional differentiation deepened, some turned into artisans, artists, sages, engineers and scientists, entirely invested in advancing the state of the art. As the specialists increasingly relied on sponsors for their livelihood, they employed their growing affluence to support the keeping of accounts and records, history and knowledge; scribes became a privileged specialty, writing an artform. Copying a handwritten book was quite laborious and only permitted under tight control, with gifts of equal value

expected in return. The copy was therefore almost as valuable as the original. All that changed when Johannes Gutenberg introduced mass production via printing, and knowledge and art could be pirated with ease and at little cost. It has reached a new quality with the proliferation of the internet and digitalization, where all codified knowledge, art and content can be accessed and copied at negligible cost, while creation remains as costly as ever.

Societies faced a dilemma: on one hand the creators needed reliable remuneration to tie their fate into furthering the state of the art. On the other hand, too tight a control on the distribution of knowledge and art would clearly curtail an individual's ability to improve himself and society as a whole. Striking the proper balance, promoting fair use while discouraging abuse, is already a complex topic at local scale; across borders and value systems, it has become a major part of politics. Today's trade wars are as much about control over immaterial assets as they are about physical resources.

Open source and intellectual property are political

Richard Stallman's main motivation to create the Free Software movement lay in the belief that locking away software source code was as immoral as the enclosure of common land in feudal England, where land ownership came to be reinterpreted by nobility in a manner that deprived commoners of the traditional usages of the area around their villages they had enjoyed since times immemorial. Resources traditionally shared by all who worked the ground gradually came under the exclusive control of a few, thus forcing villagers into contracts to work for hire or even indentures and emigration to avoid starvation.

To Stallman, source code represented human knowledge on how to solve problems, to be shared among all those who are interested and contribute, because exclusive ownership stifles the progress of society. The GNU General Public License, GPL or Copyleft was designed to ensure that all knowledge embodied in software source code published under it, would always be free to copy and use, without any indi-

vidual, company or government gaining exclusive control.

On the other hand, the English land grab also enabled a far more efficient agriculture through scale effects and created the human and capital surplus that enabled industry: pooling manpower and money under the control of a few jumpstarted the industrial revolution of which IT is a part. Patents, trademarks and copyright allowed for the steering of vast pools of talent and resources, under the direction of a few visionaries, to accelerate the development of entire industries, while hunger, sickness, war and dire needs provided the basic motivation to spur leaps of imagination and progress.

Driven to their extremes, both variants (free sharing of all things; everything under the control of a few) seem similarly capable of producing drastic innovation as well as debilitating stagnation, with the pendulum switching direction at different paces for different markets, populations, countries and value systems, causing stress, relief, strife, détente or simply change... otherwise known as progress.

Open source and competition

A very young Linus Torvalds was inspired to create his own operating system in 1991, when he read in a manual for his Intel 80386 CPU that a complete task switch—the very core functionality of a multi-tasking OS like Unix—could be achieved with a single jump instruction to a task state segment: it seemed to fit the crucial part of an OS on as little as a single page of code (currently more than half a million pages for Linux). He overlooked that this single instruction took hundreds of micro-programmed CPU cycles to execute and the resulting performance was so atrocious [1] that everybody replaced it with full routines that performed much better. His OS also had a file system so primitive that it was practically unusable. The significant advantage was that its source code, which he was proud not to use, came with a book by Andrew Tannenbaum. A book that he seems not have finished reading, because it carefully explained why monolithic kernels, like the one Torvalds was creating, were already outdated.

At the time there were two major Unix variants readily available for 32-Bit PCs: AT&T licensed System V.R3 and 386BSD, the latter of which was even open source. Both were mature, stable and performant ports from the ubiquitous VAX architecture, ensuring a rich software and user base.

Linux should have died in its crib against such competition. What changed the world of IT was that Torvalds posted his source code on the internet under the very same licence as Richard Stallman's GNU-C compiler that he had been using, incorporating its libraries and tools.

Very soon, people who actually knew how to write an operating system replaced his code. And with hundreds of developers contributing, many of them from front line research in academia, and much bigger numbers tracing bottlenecks, misfeatures or outright bugs with the help of the source code, the quality of Linux eventually eclipsed all commercial Unix variants and open source BSD. One key catalyst for open source code Linux was the social code of the GNU Copyleft, and its diode effect, which assured that all effort given freely in

contributions could not be claimed back or misappropriated by anyone, but would remain open source perpetually. Another key ingredient was Linus Torvalds's quality of judgement, from his ability to recognize and his readiness to accept superior code, to the manner in which he established community governance, or even adapted his personal code of conduct therein.

Linux and Wikipedia are the best-known examples of open collaboration initiatives, where humans are willing to invest effort into a universal body of encoded knowledge, because it feels intuitively beneficial to most, or because they become intellectually convinced it is a better approach than withholding code or content for coin. They also prove that the quality of the product, in terms of reach, functionality, resilience, diversity and completeness, can exceed what even the largest commercial or public sector entities might achieve under exclusivity, even when each individual contribution is relatively small. Where the user base or the ecosystem expands to billions, the cumulative effect of small contributions and broad oversight for digital content become so big that it creates gravity at planetary scale. And the quality of the social code, in

terms of group culture, regulation, governance and exemplary personal conduct, is a critical part of the success.

Facebook, Twitter, TikTok and WeChat show that humans will even collaborate when it is far less clear that they are to benefit the most from the effort they invest. Here the platform operators claim ownership over extracts, aggregates, insights and knowledge derived from the content their users 'share': they then sell to the highest bidder.

Open source: catalyst or bulldozer?

Superior quality, open source and zero licence cost make it difficult to compete with a commercial offering based on charging for closed source proprietary code. Putting out a begging bowl and programming like a Buddhist monk for a prayer, holds little appeal to engineer parents saving for their offspring's university tuition fees, so employers have sought elements of exclusivity to exact payment from customers. Some sell support services, warranties and certifications, others sell exclusive automation or value-added services and wherever competitors face off on level ground, a new type of price war has developed: zero

Figure 1: Mobile Operating System Global Market Share Q1 2013 – Q4 2020

Figure 2: Global Browser Market Share Q1 2009 – Q4 2020

against zero, open source against more open source, even zero against contra revenues.

In the traditional markets of yore, where people created higher value products from purchased raw materials through work, fair competition tended to reach a balance at subsistence levels, because undercutting one another leads to debt and starvation. Guilds then fixed prices a little higher to benefit their members, a practice more widely accepted then. In software production per-item cost is zero, but your ability to charge for exclusive options rises sharply, when there is little competition left for the base product. It leads to IT companies providing a commodity core without fees or even with active subsidies, to stave off competition and achieve a practical monopoly, and then charge significantly for the value-added part. Without charge there is no price fixing involved for the base product, and in that manner, they so far avoid anti-trust legislation, which has not kept up with the immaterial world of software.

Internet giants have made this approach a core aspect of their business. Their giant

user base and economy of scale has allowed them to reach a level of operational efficiency that is hard to match on-premise. And while they offer open source software components that allow workloads to onboard and take advantage of these operational gains, they do not repeat that with their secret sauce, those components which permit them to operate in such a manner: their objective is to lure customers into their proprietary clouds, not to seed competition.

To ensure Android would gain against Apple's mobile platform, Google took free and open source to battle on the client side, at a time when it seemed positioned to achieve with mobile phones what Microsoft had attained with personal computers. Covering all angles, Google made its smartphone platform: (i) open source; (ii) portable; (iii) free of charge; and (iv) irresistible, with popular apps like Maps, Mail, YouTube and Chrome included; and (v) it invested heavily into a developer ecosystem and support. Its goal was to undercut and outgrow all proprietary and licence revenue-dependent competition, and thus gain control over the platform the majority of users would use to interact with the digital

world. It then could strip mine user data on the handsets for sellable insights in order to pay for the platform support.

Its gamble paid off: Google owns the global mobile base platform [2], apart from the iPhone enclave. It managed the same with the browser [3]: again, apart from Apple's walled garden and a Firefox hold-out, it very much owns the main interface to the internet via Chrome, giving away the best open source browser for free, so nobody will be tempted to run the client side of the internet on an alternative.

In order to also crack the personal computer market with its more affluent enterprise user base and more valuable structured office data, Google created Chromebooks as a lighter, cheaper and secured PC platform, to run little more than a Google Chrome browser on an open source Linux kernel. Meanwhile, its web-based Workspace [4] acts as a cloud-based Microsoft Office replacement, with online collaboration benefits added. It removed dependence on decades of PC technology, Microsoft Windows and Office at once and enabled enterprise, government and educational use at a fraction of the opera-

tional cost. But it also created a dependency on Google cloud services, which are proprietary closed source, and for which it charges very selectively, ensuring minimal onboarding cost for habit-forming educational markets, where it has gained 60% in the United States. This dual pronged attack represented so big a threat to Microsoft that it transformed that company.

While Microsoft is following up on Google's approach to gain revenue from insights into user data, it can't easily sacrifice the revenue it obtains from the licensing closed source software. That is why Microsoft is working on moving all customers from local Office installations and document storage into their Azure cloud via Office 365. The company markets scale benefits but gains data control and plans its future on its ability to transition its exclusive hold on user habits formed during past decades to an exclusive hold on Azure for future generations. Microsoft offers Windows, Office 365 and Teams to educators at fully comprehensive prices, where open source and free licence variants lose public tenders, because their operational costs alone can be higher than a lock-in Azure offer. It balances its books by charging employers whose graduate employees are set in their habits.

Both Google and Microsoft maintain significant bodies of code and shoulder hefty expenses to operate clouds, which to them are very down-to-earth data centres. They need to develop, market, provide, operate and support it all; they give services away free to first-time users. Users' exclusive dependency on their cloud gives them dual benefits:

- It allows them to charge for profit, once customers are caught in a web of convenience or dependency;
- They can monetize all knowledge extracted and harvested from documents stored in their respective cloud with the help of AIs.

Microsoft's exclusive licence on OpenAI's GPT-3 [5] shows its determination and direction vis-à-vis Google's DeepMind acquisition. For every component and service that both offer to consumers, quality open source product alternatives are available for free, that neither create an

exclusive dependency for the back-end, nor strip mine user data for valuable knowledge. However, these alternatives require infrastructure and manpower to set up, operate and maintain from the very start. While they can offer privacy by design, and may turn out cheaper and without the risk of foreign control in the long run, the current practice of cloud giants of selling below price to "influencers" makes them look less attractive, especially when sweeping pandemic-induced changes require a fast set up.

Europe's ethical demands for open, heterogeneous and sustainable IT products and services, which put citizens with their civil liberties and privacy first, also implies a hefty burden of compliance. Similar to how US giants seed their clouds by subsidizing browsers, Web-frameworks, mobile platforms and onboarding tools, the EU must level the playing field by putting in place:

- Assets enabling that EU-generated services and products can be sold domestically and abroad with the overhead for compliance overheads removed;
- Assets enabling foreign vendors to add EU compliance to their products and services with minimal overhead;
- Taxation on the value generated from inputs via the European use base, to pay for the above efforts;
- Regulation to ensure that compliance for users within Europe's borders can be enforced and taxes can be appropriately levied across all frontiers;
- Regulation to ensure that devices and services who exceed a threshold of popularity or population must use open APIs and be made interoperable, so they need not be tied to a single vendor.

If Europe wants IoT or CPS devices to operate with embedded software stacks that employ industry's best practice during generation and are continuously updated via security patches, it may need to supply an easy and convenient equivalent of an 'IoT Chrome', so that Chinese manufacturers looking for the cheapest solution prefer using the free EU offer instead of something they had a freelance student assemble years ago on a penny budget.

If Europe wants IoT or CPS devices from different vendors to work with virtual digital assistants on any cloud without the servant selling its loyalty to the highest bidder, the EU needs to put in place quite a few free building blocks which offset the overhead in development cost and complexity. It must then use regulation to ensure that, at least for the internal market, Alexa, Siri or Google's assistant don't profit from shortcuts in privacy or security.

Open source suffers the same fate as any other tool devised by humans. The first stick was used to dig out a nourishing root but, perhaps a minute later, it was also used to decide who would eat it. While open source was created with the idealistic motive to create fairness by maximizing knowledge sharing, one of its major use cases today is to remove fairness from corporate battles.

Why Europe needs to enforce and support open source

When code becomes used by the majority of people most of the time, every automated decision it makes becomes a political choice. When such decisions are even potentially made without the sanction or indeed against the local laws, culture or ethics, actions should be taken to ensure that the code or application follows rules, quite independently of how the code actually performs, or its original purpose and scope.

Google, Facebook, WeChat, WhatsApp, Tiktok or Twitter were not originally designed for the transformative power on society that they hold today, just like the first editions of MS-DOS, Unix, Android or Mosaic never aimed to run the planet.

Today, a ban on Google's Search, Android and Chrome or Microsoft's Windows and Office could completely cripple Europe, while similar bans on Facebook, WhatsApp and Twitter might just do the opposite. With decisions taken recently by the US government, what seemed like a remote possibility a few years ago has become a real threat everyone needs to plan for. It also became the urgently required wake-up call that the natural threshold of intervention against the 'legislative power'

of web-giant code was actually crossed a long time ago.

Defensive measures: reducing the attack surface

Proprietary closed source products from companies which can be coerced by governments outside the EU and which cannot be easily substituted, must be regarded as a threat to European sovereignty.

It is not much better if the products are open source, but encumbered by licences or intellectual property restrictions that prohibit their continued use in case of trade conflicts. If those restrictions cannot be negotiated or regulated away, substitution is required.

Social media or content platforms with algorithmic transformation of content need to be matched to political borders and either opened for regulation or blocked. Privacy can be viewed as a very local censorship bias and achieved when regulation works.

Enabling measures: increasing market potential

When Europe wants to impose restrictions on how web-giants strip mine all data that flows through their platform for sellable insights, those might counter by reducing their services and stopping

the distribution of the client-side assets. Android, the Google Search/Play Store/Chrome/Maps/Mail etc. might have to be replaced by local alternatives as they are in China already and for Huawei especially, which may cause significant inconvenience for the existing European user base, but no essential loss.

If Europe prepares itself to take up the slack, it doesn't have to start from scratch: for Linux, Android, Office and most other "digital essentials", most assets are open source. Even if their vendors stopped their distribution in the EU, they could be substituted with funding perhaps not too different to what European customers currently pay in licensing fees.

It also becomes an opportunity to break up the inherent link between the corporate business model and corporate ethics, and to insert modularity and compatibility with greater variances in local ethics and content regulation. It is a two-sided sword, which can deliver far better control for achieving civil liberties and privacy for EU consumers, but would also enable more undemocratic government controls elsewhere. Europe could contribute to a truly global code base, if it is prepared to completely separate out business model and ethics to make them modular and configurable.

There is no reason why even China, Iran, Cuba or North Korea might not want to collaborate with the EU on a single code base for all digital essentials, if everybody gets what they want, nothing of what they don't and can rest assured that nobody can hijack the project or critical parts of it. Even Google, Facebook and the UK might join back in eventually, when the governance is done right.

Perhaps most importantly, providing a PC, server, smartphone and IoT platform independent from domination via foreign governments enables the market of trillions of smart device instances. In such a market, cyber-physical systems that have all the virtues and qualities Europe demands can be created: full sovereignty for the owners of virtual personal assistants, their knowledge base and the devices they manage, with all the necessary loyalty, discretion, sustainability and security to give them significant value.

Open source needs more support

Wikipedia [6] is a prime example of open source content creation and curation that manages to do without paying the vast majority of its contributors; while the quality and value thus generated is hard to gauge, unless it is monetized via its use as carefully curated input for the latest machine learning models.

Figure 3: Wikipedia topic breakdown 2016 [7]

Image: ID 35101825 | ©Adonis1969 | Dreamstime.com

More traditional open source programming language code creation and curation is a more specialized skill, the main line of work for many contributors, who need income to continue.

However, since the resulting bodies of encoded knowledge are free to use for everyone, the exclusivity typically required to exact payment is missing and, when programmers and their families go hungry, their contributions stop. If Europe wants open source assets to level the playing field against competition, it needs to find more ways to provide a living for those who contribute to this digital commodities infrastructure.

The earliest forms of government likely arose from trading: swapping wares, because both sides had a surplus of one good while they needed another. Setting up a market, creating space, roads, rules and their enforcement was an effort paid for in taxes.

While taxes were levied at every bridge during the middle ages, once realms and roads connected and news spread how roads and bridges should be built and markets operated, it became clear that there was little benefit to having a cut-throat competition between roads, bridges and markets right next to each other. That is to say, an aggregated or even centralized

government-controlled infrastructure gave better commodity benefits and enabled the competition to move up and into new green fields of innovation.

Wherever one or very few competitors are left with little differentiation but scale, these tend to invest their profits more into solidifying their stranglehold than into improving their services. At that point, the majority service vendor effectively assumes a government function and that's where a government that wants to retain its sovereignty needs to step in.

The digital commodities required to simply participate in a digital world can be

considered the equivalent of what governments deliver in the physical world. While we pay for our own shoes (smartphones) and cars (laptops), governments provide sidewalks and roads (OS, browser), regulation and enforcement, financed via taxes. Competition can still have a significant place there, just like road-building or other major infrastructure projects are segmented and publicly tendered.

Modern cities invest in much more than just basic commodities like roads, marketplaces and water supply. They feature public transportation, educational institutions, incubators, even public internet sometimes, because they believe that cut-throat competition for these commodities doesn't really help to achieve their real target: the best infrastructure to support a wide diversity and depth of new businesses.

Qualities of open source

Open source has evolved and diversified in recent decades: there are many variants and business models, but all of them rely on rules being followed, and social code and governance being properly executed as well. Such cooperation is natural to humans, but we switch into competition when threatened or when we judge the gains high enough. This leads to cyberwar that carries significant risks. But at least it tends to halt code evolution only at the point where collaboration was lost. All code and content distributed up to that point remains available to everyone with a local copy, because there is no centralized control. Proprietary software and exclusive services are much easier to choke off completely, with crippling and devastating effects.

Open source provides tangible incentives for international collaboration, and

more efficient and stable algorithms benefit everyone who needs them. The more widespread the use of certain pieces of code, the more everyone depends on them being stable and efficient, and the more likely they are to motivate collaboration even across value divides. While open source doesn't automatically deserve trust, it is even more difficult to trust closed source. Where the two compete, open source is likely to win. Where code is really critical, either because it is used everywhere (e.g. browser or shared library) or where its use is critical for security, open source enables such a scrutiny and widespread willingness to improve it, that it out-evolves proprietary solutions. It should be noted that open source alone doesn't guarantee quality: practically all student homework today is hosted on open repositories from the very start of their learning curve. And in an environment where the rate of adoption by other developers for a new niche or use case can seem more important than its readiness for production, quality can suffer.

While we used to view code as something technical or mathematical at the dawn of computer science, code and data have been somewhat irreversibly mingled very early on and today quite simply are encoded knowledge and content which co-evolve with the human species. Being open about knowledge and sharing freely typically helps growth when there is little competition or resource constraints. When scarcity has competition heat up, closing down can help win a battle or a war, and accelerate the development of a few vs. a bulk left behind, at the risk of losing all. Neither strategy guarantees long-term success: we recommend switching intelligently and swiftly between the two approaches.

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